

Generative AI-powered Chronic Kidney Disease Exam Candidates' Practice Test with Self-Grading

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Abstract. Self-assessment plays a crucial role by enabling medical students to evaluate their knowledge and competency [1].

In this article, we introduce a Cognitive Application driven by Generative AI, designed to facilitate automatic self-assessment for candidates preparing for exams on chronic kidney disease.

The performance of this Cognitive Application is evaluated by comparing candidates' responses to a ten-question oral questionnaire administered by a human investigator with the outcomes generated by the AI solution.

The Cognitive Application demonstrated a remarkably high level of accuracy: candidates participating in this study confirmed its usefulness and reliability.

The proposed Artificial Intelligence solution for self-assessing exam candidates' knowledge proves to be effective, innovative, and precise, with potential applicability to other medical fields of study.

Keywords: Medical students, Self-assessment, Micro-facial expressions, Artificial Intelligence, Generative AI, Cognitive Application, Large Language Model (LLM), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Multimodal Learning.

1 Principles underpinning the Cognitive Application

This article describes the Generative AI Cognitive Application that we have developed with the aim of assisting medical students in evaluating their exam readiness through a simulated examination process.

The Cognitive Robot records video footage of each exam simulation. Subsequently, it conducts an in-depth analysis of the video, providing candidates with comprehensive feedback, including overall assessments ("Ready" versus "non-Ready") and distinctions between correct and incorrect responses.

Initially, the Cognitive Robot is equipped with training documentation [2] which contains essential knowledge that candidates are required to study.

During the exam simulation session, the Cognitive Robot autonomously generates ten open-ended questions to present to the candidate. Concurrently, it records video footage of the candidate's responses within a session lasting approximately 15 minutes.

Upon the completion of the recording session, the Cognitive Robot assesses the accuracy and completeness of the responses by referring to the training documentation and computes the overall score of the exam simulation by evaluating each candidate's response. Furthermore, the Cognitive Application evaluates the candidate's microfacial expressions while answering each question, to gauge students' self-confidence.

The efficacy of the Cognitive Application was assessed by comparing the outcomes of candidates' knowledge evaluation using two distinct methods:

- Cognitive Application-based entailed: students participating in an exam simulation session used the Cognitive Application for answering a list of automatically generated open-ended questions.
- Human Investigator-based: candidates' readiness was assessed through an oral questionnaire consisting of the same ten questions asked by the Robot.

2 Cognitive Application components

The Cognitive Application comprises two primary AI components:

- Natural Language Engine (“NLE”), for natural language comprehension, processing, and generation, which integrates an open-source LLM (large language model), fine-tuned using the training documentation [2].
- Multimodal Sentiment Analyzer (“MSA”), designed to detect emotions from the exam candidates' video by utilizing:
 - Microfacial expressions from images/frames and the entire video.
 - Audio nuances.
 - Text extracted from speech-to-text conversion.

The Multimodal Sentiment Analyzer (MSA) module is a CNN-based component specifically crafted to detect the seven fundamental emotions delineated by Paul Ekman [3]: Happiness, Sadness, Fear, Disgust, Anger, Contempt, and Surprise (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Example of facial expressions' analysis

3 Results achieved

The "Exam Readiness threshold" has been initially set to 80%. Consequently, if the calculated Exam Readiness percentage falls below 80%, the student should postpone the exam session. Conversely, a value exceeding 80% indicates the student's readiness.

The "Exam Readiness %" is computed during an oral questionnaire with the Human Investigator and a session conducted with the Cognitive Robot, representing the average sum of percentages obtained across ten open-ended questions. By comparing the results of two sessions, we have verified that both approaches provided consistent results in assessing exam readiness, as represented in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of Exam Readiness % values achieved.

ID	Student	Exam Readiness %		Mean Squared Error (MSE) calculation
		Human Investigator (y)	Cognitive Robot (p)	
1	Student 1	83.3%	78.7% ⁽¹⁾	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0021$
2	Student 2	100.0%	96.3%	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0014$
3	Student 3	91.6%	93.2%	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0003$
4	Student 4	83.3%	86.7%	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0012$
5	Student 5	100.0%	100.0%	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0000$
6	Student 6	83.3%	82.1%	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0001$
7	Student 7	83.3%	81.8%	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0002$
8	Student 8	100.0%	98.6%	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0002$
9	Student 9	83.3%	85.4%	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0004$
10	Student 10	83.3%	86.8%	$(y-p)^2 = 0,0012$
MSE				0,07%

4 Conclusions

The Cognitive Application proved 90% accuracy compared to human assessment. Students' satisfaction surveys confirmed its effectiveness. The tool, abides at ethical guidelines, enables self-assessments, continuous improvement and academic excellence.

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